

randomized block design with three replications. Fertilizer (80 kg N/ha) was applied in 3 equal splits: at transplanting, 20 d after transplanting, and at panicle initiation.

The season was cloudy, with less than 4.5 h of bright light/d. Periodic samples were taken for leaf area index (LAI), total dry matter (TDM), and crop growth rate (CGR). Photosynthetic rates (Pn) of the second leaf before flowering and the flag leaf at flowering were measured with LI-6000 Portable Photosynthesis System; maintenance respiration (MR) was measured by Gilson differential respirometer. Crop photosynthesis is assumed to be $Pn \times LAI$.

Yield and yield attributes were recorded at harvest. Given a high frequency of sterile plants in the hybrids, 20 normal fertile plants were taken for yield assessment. Standard heterosis was calculated over check Jaya.

Considerable standard heterosis was apparent in Pn, LAI, and $Pn \times LAI$ at 30 d after planting and in post-flowering CGR, TDM, and yield (see table). Heterosis of MR was negative. Panicle number and grain number/m² exhibited high heterosis. The hybrid with Madhu A showed good heterosis in Pn, MR, and Pn/MR at flowering (F).

Among the hybrids with IR54752 A, Swarna and IR54 hybrids combined

Standard heterosis for physiological characters and yield of rice hybrids, Cuttack, India, 1989 wet season.

Character ^a	Standard check Jaya	Standard heterosis (%) of hybrids over						
		IR54752 A						Jaya
		IR54 (UAS)	IR54 (CRR1)	IR27- 31.5	Prabhat	Swarna	Pratiba	Madhu A/ IR15324
Pn at 30 d (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	28.1	22	8	20	12	8	9	17
Flowering	34.6	4	5	-11	-11	-14	4	23
MR at flowering	2.6	-9	4	-14	-7	-14	-14	12
Pn/MR at flowering	8.9	0	3	0	-17	-7	4	18
$Pn \times LAI$ (F) gCO ₂ /m ²	11.3	35	22	11	-2	3	-13	19
LAI at 30 d	0.92	39	31	4	19	42	6	3
Flowering	3.28	42	16	25	9	20	-9	4
SLW at flowering (mg/dm ²)	520	8	11	12	-2	4	18	-14
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	29.3	22	19	17	11	26	14	4
FL SLW (mg/dm ²)	541	2	7	5	8	3	9	-9
TDM at 30 d (g/m ²)	88	30	39	-2	4	22	9	-2
Flowering	870	23	11	40	-16	40	14	-26
Harvest	1051	60	62	66	26	54	28	13
CGR at 0-30 d (g/m ² per d)	2.93	30	39	-2	4	24	9	-2
50 d tooflowering	14.7	15	3	15	48	6	-10	8
Flowering-harvest	6.0	243	311	190	226	123	96	203
Yield (g/m ²)	384	68	73	77	2	71	17	7
Yield (g/m ² per d)	2.9	59	62	59	0	55	7	14
Panicles/m ²	177	53	52	52	33	33	28	23
Grains/panicle (no.)	87.7	3	4	9	-21	45	-16	-7
Grains/m ² ($\times 10^2$)	155	56	45	65	4	94	7	-25
1000-grain wt (g)	26.3	4	-7	6	0	-11	-7	-22
HI (%)	36	6	8	8	-17	11	-8	4

^aPn = photosynthetic rate, MR = maintenance respiration rate, LAI = leaf area index, TDM = total dry matter, CGR = crop growth rate, SLW = specific leaf wt, FL SLW = flag leaf specific leaf wt

strong heterosis in LAI, TDM, and yield, but heterosis in Pn at flowering and CGR at reproductive growth was poor. Heterosis for photosynthesis in these

hybrids might be improved by combining them with photosynthetically effective restorers. □

Meiotic behavior of some WA cytosterile lines

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The meiotic behavior of CMS lines IR46827 A, IR46828 A, IR46829 A, and IR46830 A was studied to ascertain chromosomal abnormality associated with pollen abortion or sterility.

Meiosis of microsporogenesis showed 12 regular, well-developed bivalents at diakinesis and metaphase I with a normal 12:12 separation of chromosomes at anaphase I; 3 secondary associations of 2 bivalents each in a large number of

Meiotic behavior of chromosomes in 4 CMS lines.

CMS line	Pollen				Remarks
	mother cell scored (no.)	Diakinesis	Metaphase I	Anaphase I	
IR46827 A	50	12 II	12 II	12:12	Chromatin becomes feeble in anaphase I and dis-integrates completely in telophase I.
IR46828 A	50	12 II	12 II	12:12	
IR46829 A	50	12 II	12 II	12:12	
IR46830 A	50	12 II	12 II	12:12	

preparations; a variable number and behavior of nucleoli; and a gradual disintegration of chromatin setting in at anaphase I, resulting in its complete disappearance by late telophase I (see table).

Complete sterility of microspores in all CMS lines showed that they belonged to the CPA (complete pollen abortion)

type. In this type, meiosis initially progresses normally, but the microspores tend to abort. Total absence of chromatin matter at telophase I is a new report of a cytological basis for pollen abortion in CMS lines. Imbalance of synthesis and degradation of auxins could be the reason for pollen abortion and complete sterility. □